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New record of the alien Nearctic species *Callopistromyia annulipes* (MACQUART, 1885) (Diptera: Ulidiidae) from Poland

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Abstract: *Callopistromyia annulipes*, an alien peacock fly, is recorded in Lubusz Province (West of Poland) for the first time. Locality and habitat characteristics are briefly described.

Key words: peacock fly, biogeography, expansion, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION AND RESULTS

The peacock fly *Callopistromyia annulipes* (MACQUART, 1885) is one of two known species of the genus *Callopistromyia* HENDEL, 1907 (Diptera: Ulidiidae). This species known from the Nearctic – USA, Canada (STEYSKAL 1979, KAMENEVA & KORNEYEV 2006) and was first recorded in Europe in 2007 (MERZ 2008), in Switzerland. In the following years, *C. annulipes* spread through Europe rapidly. Until now, *C. annulipes* has been recorded from Germany (MERZ & GYSEGHEM 2008, ROLKE 2017, STARK 2017), Italy (NIOLU 2009, KORNEYEV *et al.* 2014), the Netherlands (SMIT & HAMERS 2011), Austria (KORNEYEV *et al.* 2014, ZITTRA *et al.* 2017), France (KORNEYEV *et al.* 2014), Slovakia (KORNEYEV *et al.* 2014, DVOŘÁK *et al.* 2017, STLOUKAL & STLOUKALOVÁ 2017), Slovenia (KORNEYEV *et al.* 2014, DVOŘÁK *et al.* 2017), Hungary (KAMENEVA & PEKARSKY 2016), Belgium (RAVOET & FARINELLE 2017), Czech Republic (DVOŘÁK 2017), Poland (KLASA & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2018), and Ukraine (DVOŘÁK *et al.* 2019).

In Poland, the first record of this species was reported in 2018 (KLASA & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2018) from Wrocław. New records on the occurrence of *C. annulipes* in Poland are presented below.

One specimen of the *C. annulipes* was observed on 3 June 2019 in the central part of the Lubusz Province, in the Pliszka River valley (52.247799N, 15.174069E) by Roland E. and

Iakushenko D. (Fig. 1). The locality is situated within ‘Natura 2000’ area PLH080011 Dolina Pliszki (MACIANTOWICZ 2012).

The species was observed and photographed on the exposed to sun wooden railing right on the river bank (Fig. 2), on the edge of the riparian gallery floodplain forest dominated by *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) GAERTN., with *Carex acutiformis* EHRH., *C. appropinquata* SCHUMACH., *C. elongata* L., *C. riparia* CURTIS, *Iris pseudacorus* L., *Phragmites australis* (CAV.) STEUD., *Solanum dulcamara* L. etc. in herbal layer. This habitat was assigned as habitat 91E0 Alluvial forests with *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior* (*Alno-Padion*, *Alnion incanae*, *Salicion albae*) (PAWLACZYK 2010). Remarkably, a lot of standing dead black alder trunks occur along the river (Figs. 2, 3).

Photos of the observed specimen (Figs. 4–6) were taken in the field using digital camera Canon 500d and Nikon D5200.

Fig. 1. Geographic locality of peacock fly *Callopietromyia annulipes* in Lubusz Province (W Poland).

REMARKS

The report is a contribution to tracking the extension of the range of occurrence of non-native species and in the long run to observing the processes and changes in the composition of the fauna of individual geographical regions.

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Fig. 2. Habitat of *Callopietromyia annulipes* (photo D. Iakushenko).

Fig. 3. Habitat of *Callopietromyia annulipes* (photo D. Iakushenko).

Fig. 4. *Callopistromyia annulipes* sitting on a wooden railing on the bank of the Pliszka river (photo E. Roland).

Fig. 5. *Callopistromyia annulipes* sitting on a wooden railing on the bank of the Pliszka river (photo D. Iakushenko).

Fig. 6. *Callopietromyia annulipes* sitting on a wooden railing on the bank of the Pliszka river (photo D. Iakushenko).

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